

IMPORTANCE OF MARKETING SERVICE IN ENTERPRISES IN THE CONDITIONS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article examines the connection with market activity in furniture production enterprises: choosing a market, determining the volume of sales, planning and setting the perspective of market activity, studying market subjects, the form and methods of trading in the market.

Keywords: enterprise, market, strategy, entity, need, demand, export, import, object.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СЛУЖБЫ МАРКЕТИНГА НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ В УСЛОВИЯХ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ СТРАТЕГИИ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается связь с рыночной деятельностью предприятий по производству мебели: выбор рынка, определение объема продаж, планирование и постановка перспективы рыночной деятельности, изучение субъектов рынка, формы и методов торговли на рынке.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, рынок, стратегия, субъект, потребность, спрос, экспорт, импорт, объект.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the furniture and woodworking industry occupies an important place in the world economy. In 2021, the global furniture production volume will be 425 billion US dollars, which is more than 0.5% of the gross production volume. In recent years, the average annual growth rate of this industry was 2.6%. The diagram below shows the distribution of office furniture, a type of furniture products, by country.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The construction of residential and commercial facilities in Uzbekistan ensures a constant increase in the need for furniture. Another factor is that the increase in the purchasing power of the population is causing a rapid increase in the demand for furniture products. Today, 90% of the capacity of the furniture market of our country is covered by the products of local producers. There are more than 5,300 woodworking enterprises in the republic, which produce not only furniture, but also construction materials such as MDF, plywood, and laminate. More than 300,000 workers are employed in Sokha enterprises.

The export capacity of Sokha enterprises is also increasing day by day. Based on the data of 2020, the largest consumer is Kazakhstan, to which 1500 thousand US dollars were exported. Kyrgyzstan (917.1 thousand), Tajikistan (458.7 thousand), Russia (187.2 thousand), Singapore (116 thousand), India (101.7 thousand), Turkey (97.1 thousand), Slovenia (51, 2), Saudi Arabia (49.7 thousand), Germany (29.3 thousand) and the USA (11.3 thousand).

The development of the furniture industry has been in the focus of attention of the head of our country. An example of this is the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 21, 2021. An example is the Decision "On measures aimed at the development of the furniture industry in the territories of the republic". Based on this decision, a new approach to the furniture industry is envisaged, and the development of furniture clusters is defined, including small

industrial zones specializing in the production of furniture products have been established in the regions.

According to the decision, furniture clusters are given a number of benefits, namely:

a) production areas in small industrial zones are realized through an electronic online auction on the basis of property rights;

b) as a mandatory condition for ownership of production areas in small industrial zones, according to the master plan of this small industrial zone, the location of furniture and its component parts production and sales facilities is determined;

c) the part of the proceeds from the sale of land used in agriculture in the small industrial zone through an electronic online auction on the basis of property rights, directed to the local budget, is formed as an additional income of the budget, and at least 30 percent is used for the inclusion of new land areas in this area for agriculture;

g) activities of construction of external engineering and communication networks of small industrial zones: construction, reconstruction of drinking water, sewage networks and roads for repair works - funds provided in the state budget for 2021-2023; construction, reconstruction and repair works of electricity, natural gas and communication networks are carried out at the expense of the supplier enterprises in the established order.

The procedure for the development of the "Program for the development of the furniture and woodworking industry in Uzbekistan in 2021-2024" is established, which provides for the following:

- introduction of new types and packages of consumer loans for equipping the multi-apartment houses being built in the regions of the republic, primarily with local furniture products, based on the demand of the population;
- Approval of the furniture renewal schedule of state organizations in the territories of the republic, including preschool education, general secondary and secondary special education, and health care institutions in 2021-2024;
- cultivation of tree species used as raw materials in all directions of the furniture industry, taking into account the climatic conditions of the republic, and establishment of plantations of tree species used as raw materials in the furniture industry of the republic;
- launch of production facilities in the republic by large furniture manufacturing companies in foreign countries (China, Turkey and European countries);
- Together with the Ministry of Innovative Development and "Ozkimyosanoat" JSC, implementation of projects aimed at the production of MDF boards, HPL panels, as well as raw materials, spare parts, fittings and accessories specified in Annex 2 of this decision in the territories of the republic.

RESULTS

Implementation of the President's Decision puts not only investment and production tasks before the furniture manufacturing enterprises, but also the tasks of moving the product and increasing the export capacity. From a methodological point of view, these tasks are closely related to marketing services in the field. Today, marketing services mean a wide range of services. Although their names and directions are different, their tasks are almost the same - to create an environment for the development of marketing activities for a manufacturing enterprise. Today, the following types of marketing services are popular, and we will briefly describe them:

SMM- Social Media Marketing.

Contains a list of tasks that can be performed together or separately. This includes maintaining pages on social networks, for which it is necessary to first perform superficial or in-depth analysis, choose a design and review the content plan. And setting up targeted ads with conversions based on analysis results. Today, almost every business can find its target audience on social media, so having a page on each of them is more of a necessity than a fashion statement.

Media advertising. Also called banner. With its help, a business can expand its presence in the market and reach a wider audience.

Working with the reputation of the enterprise. Here, Internet marketing services are divided into two types: SERM and Internet PR. The first involves working with opinions when reputations are damaged. The user enters the name of the company in the search and sees only positive comments and materials about it. However, experts recommend working with this area regardless of the situation to avoid potential problems. PR, in turn, enhances this reputation by creating a brand image with strong positive associations. This helps to maintain and increase the level of the company in the eyes of users.

Email marketing. A service whose name speaks for itself. A step-by-step study of the e-mail sending strategy is carried out with its subsequent implementation. An expert sets up an email funnel and creates a detailed content plan that encourages users to open the email, read it, and follow the link. True, there is a possibility that the system will filter it. In this case, additional cleaning is necessary so that the letter does not end up in spam.

Video advertisement. If necessary, a marketing services company can undertake both the creation of individual clips and the development of the concept for a series of commercials, as well as their distribution.

Special projects. In medium and large businesses, individual advertising communications aimed at attracting and local incentives to purchase through interest are used.

Consulting. It is likely that the business owner himself cannot objectively find the cause of the stagnation or eliminate it. In such a situation, external help is needed. An experienced specialist analyzes the company's strengths and weaknesses, development dynamics, and then makes recommendations for further actions. Perhaps it will suggest new directions for business development. You can ask for specific help or order an integrated approach. The latter, as a rule, gives better results, because it affects several types of communication at the same time and, accordingly, affects the results of the advertising campaign.

Contextual advertising. It is used in B2B and B2C segments. This type of ad is similar to the ad that appears in search results when a user types in keywords.

Analytics (analytical service). It involves a broad and in-depth study of the market and the key niche in terms of target audience and competitors. New directions are being selected. Of course, the business itself is studied: advertising strategies and advertising campaigns, their effectiveness, development opportunities, etc. Services can be provided separately or in combination.

Development of marketing strategy. This includes everything from analytics to media planning. This service is most in demand among small business entities, because such companies

sometimes do not have their own specialist or their employee does not have the required level of qualification.

SEO and site work. Marketing services for business promotion include a comprehensive study of all channels to attract the target audience. Among them, there is a site where you need to create design, usability, technical settings. A specialist will deal with your Internet resource, making it meet business goals and the requirements of search engines. It is a complex and painstaking task, which is appreciated by both small businesses and large enterprises.

Determining the structure of marketing management means defining individual elements in the subject of marketing management, their subordination to each other, and determining their interrelationships in management decision-making and implementation. Such subordination and interaction can be different. This justifies the diversity of management structures. The following are most commonly considered:

- functional structure of management;
- management structure based on the commodity principle (commodity structure of management);
- management structure based on the regional principle (regional management structure);
- matrix management structure.

The most important stage in the process of conducting marketing research is their precise organization. The forms of organization of marketing research can be different: it uses its own research, involving foreign companies or in a mixed way.

Only large firms with a dedicated department can handle marketing research on their own. Small firms can apply to a special organization or merge with other enterprises to transfer them. The majority of foreign firms prefer to use a mixed form in the organization of marketing research. Generally, outside organizations are tasked with conducting mass consumer surveys. In practice, all reputable foreign firms cooperate with market research institutes and (or) consulting organizations.

Importance of decision making in marketing. First of all, let's look at the directions of marketing research before making a decision. They are usually carried out in 5 major directions.

1. Advertising organization studies (inspiring buyers, advertising tests, types of advertising and their comparative effectiveness, etc.).
2. Strategic planning and organizational policy (short- and long-term forecasting and enterprise results, analysis of market locations, opportunities for new diversification development, operational gross analysis, analysis of the internal environment of the organization, export market observations, etc.).
3. Research on organizational responsibility (social responsibility of the organization on customer formation, environmental protection, etc.).
4. Market analysis (customer attitude to new goods, potential and opportunities of new goods, testing of new goods, problems of product coding and its verification, etc.).
5. Sales opportunities and marketing research (identification of competent or potential markets, analysis of market composition, analysis of changes in sales volume, conducting test marketing, studying sales promotion procedures, etc.).

We will consider marketing research as a whole process and the tasks it should solve in detail in the next parts.

DISCUSSION

All the information collected in the marketing field is composed of analytical methods, developments, decision-making models, and computer programs as a decision-making subsystem in message management. It is natural that decisions made within the framework of management are based on certain sources and analytical results.

Marketing goals and objectives are defined in the section of the plan. A marketing objective is a final result that is intended to be achieved through marketing. Such final results are determined in relation to goods, consumers and markets. At the same time, the solution of the tasks expressed should ensure the achievement of the set goals. These objectives are required to:

- quantitatively based;
- ranked in order of importance;
- achieved in a certain period of time;
- real, i.e. it can be done in reality.

The fifth section of the plan deals with marketing strategies. Each such strategy envisages the implementation of a set of compatible measures that ensure the achievement of a specific goal. Such measures mean the following:

- market segmentation;
- identifying the target market;
- placement of goods and services in target segments;
- determining methods of entering the target market;
- development of marketing mix;
- time to market.

After the marketing strategies are determined, the sixth section of the plan develops an action program that specifies:

- what is done;
- when will it be done;
- who does;
- what resources are needed.

The seventh section of the plan shows the general estimate of marketing expenses. The costs of certain elements of the product movement policy, such as advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, and public relations, are also presented here.

The last section of the marketing plan describes the procedure of control over the implementation of the specified measures. Such control allows to evaluate the results of the company's activity and to take necessary measures to eliminate the detected deficiencies. Special attention is paid to the analysis of the achieved sales volume and the amount of profit obtained from it.

In order to ensure their viability in the conditions of a changing market economy, enterprises in operation will have to comprehensively analyze their strengths and weaknesses. The SWOT-analysis method is used to carry out this analysis. Based on this method, the company's strengths (S) and weaknesses (W), opportunities (O) and risks (T) are determined.

In recent years, as a result of the strengthening of the following three trends, it has been possible to collect marketing information in a better and wider scale.

1. Moving from local level marketing to general marketing scale. As firms and businesses constantly expand their market territory, it becomes increasingly difficult for their managers to get to know all of their customers personally. Therefore, it is necessary to find new

ways to collect and organize marketing information, to determine the scope of information necessary for further marketing research.

2. Transition from consumer need to consumer demand. As consumers' incomes increase, they become more discerning in their choice of goods and services, so it is necessary to find criteria that can easily explain consumer behavior. Studying the causes of consumer demand, identifying unsatisfied needs and requirements, dividing consumers into groups (segments) who demand different goods and services according to the type, quality and quantity, and trying to find a separate, unique demand within each segment through marketing research.

3. Shifting to non-price competition instead of price competition. Thanks to scientific and technical advances, favorable conditions are created for the use of methods of competition that are not related to price. becomes the main factor of competition. At such times, information on "how the market is affected by the methods used" becomes important. In such conditions, enterprises and firms start placing orders for conducting marketing research. In the conditions of the market economy, enterprises and firms will not be able to control the market unless the goods and services are coordinated according to the actual needs and requirements of the consumers.

Marketing research involves organizing, collecting, processing and analyzing information. Such organization helps enterprises and firms to make marketing decisions in their activities and to reduce uncertainties as much as possible. Marketing is the object of research and serves the market, goods, trade (commerce), competitors, buyers, pricing, advertising, opportunities for enterprises or firms. The unique qualities of conducting marketing research are that it helps to choose the strategy and tactics of the enterprise and marketing activities and implement it on the basis of the conducted specific research. The content of marketing research is determined by its goals and objectives and requires two interrelated aspects: researching a specific market and researching the possibilities of enterprises or firms to enter the market and take a strong position there. Market research is the most common field of marketing research. It is conducted to collect information about the market in order to determine the activity of the enterprise.

According to the experts, it is related to market activity: continuous collection, analysis and comparison of all the information necessary to make important decisions such as market selection, determining the volume of trade, planning market activity and defining the perspective, studying market subjects, the form and methods of trading in the market. impossible without research. In order to carry out marketing research, it is necessary to create such organizational departments in enterprises and firms that these departments can fully and fully implement the marketing concept. without marketing knowledge in the conditions of the current market economy, that is, the study of customer demand for product quality and characteristics, future demand.

CONCLUSIONS

Departments conducting marketing research should conduct their research and research on the basis of accepted principles of pure competition, and these studies should be based on scientific methods and based on accepted international standards. The information prepared on the basis of the researches of the marketing department serves as a basis for informing intermediaries, suppliers, and manufacturers about the requirements and views, habits of a wide range of consumers. The results of departments conducting marketing research help to manage the company's activities, to expand production and sales by finding the needs of customers.

Therefore, specialists of this department should not mislead the management of the enterprise by overestimating their capabilities. It is strictly forbidden to give the problems and research results assigned to the specialists of this department to outsiders and enterprises. The cooperation of the department conducting marketing research is primarily necessary for the following purposes: analysis of daily (weekly, monthly, annual) work situations, determination of prospective directions of the enterprise in the conditions of changing market conditions, concern for the consumer and product quality, presentation of developments based on the purpose of making optimal decisions to find the best ways to use limited resources by the enterprise.

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